

ACOUSTO-ULTRASONIC CHARACTERISTICS FOR CONTACT-TYPE TRANSDUCERS COUPLED TO A COMPOSITE BEAM

S. Kitipornchai¹, T. Liu², and K. M. Liew³

¹ *Department of Civil Engineering, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Qld. 4072, Australia*

² *Department of Aircraft Engineering, Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics Nanjing, 210016, P. R. China*

³ *School of Mechanical and Production Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*

SUMMARY: Acousto-ultrasonic technique is finding an increased usage among the nondestructive evaluation of composite materials. In this paper the acousto-ultrasonic characteristics for transmitting and receiving contact-type transducers coupled to a composite beam are considered. Through introducing some simplifying assumptions for the transducers, an analytical method which can deal with all wave processes involved with the system, i.e. wave generation, wave propagation and wave reception, is developed. Using this method, the spectral response of the normal contact stress sensed by the receiving transducer, due to an arbitrary input pulse excited by the transmitting transducer, is expressed in the form of explicit physical interpretations. The time history of the contact stress output for the receiver is obtained by using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) technique. Finally, from some numerical results the acousto-ultrasonic characteristics are discussed.

KEYWORDS: acousto-ultrasonic technique analysis, contact-type transducers, composite material evaluation, elastic wave propagation

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing use of advanced composites in many engineering structures, it is of growing importance to employ reliable and effective nondestructive evaluation (NDE) methods to determine the quality and mechanical serviceability of these materials. In recent years, an analytical ultrasonic NDE technique or stress wave factor (SWF) technique presented by Vary [1] has been receiving considerable attention. It has been found that this technique is especially useful for providing a measurable quantitative parameter which correlates well with mechanical properties of various composite materials such as stiffness, strength and fatigue life.

For the purposes of understanding this technique, the dispersion of the ultrasonic wave propagation in composite materials has been considered by many researchers; for instance Duke, Henneke et al.[2], Datta et al.[3], and Kim et al.[4]. Also, the quantitative features of the elastic wave field generated in composite laminates by surface pulses have been studied by Mal and Lih [5,6], Ditri and Rose [7] and etc. Furthermore, the problems of dynamic response of a transducer to waves, and wave propagation in a cracked composite plate have been recently investigated by the authors and other investigators [8,9]. It can be seen that

previous investigations relevant to the AU technique are all only concerned with one stage of the AU technique, since as is known, the AU technique consists of three basic physical stages: wave generation, wave propagation and wave reception. It is evident that in order to completely examine the AU results and hence study the stress wave factor the synthetical analysis of the three stages of the AU technique is further required.

Owing to the complexities involved, in the previous investigations, however, there seems to be only the work of Williams et al.[10] concerning this problem. The ultrasonic input-output model for transmitting and receiving transducers coupled to an isotropic elastic plate was investigated by tracing the multiple reflections of waves in the plate excited by a single tone burst input. Since it is based on the asymptotic solution for an isotropic half-space subjected to harmonic normal surface pulses, this model has many limitations, especially the difficulty in extending to the case of composite structures.

In this paper an analytical method for the investigation of the ultrasonic input-output characteristics of transmitting and receiving contact-type transducers coupled to a composite beam is developed. With the aid of some simplifying assumptions on transducers the governing equations for the AU system involved with wave emission, wave propagation and wave reception, are first established. Using a multiple integral transform method and contour integral technique, the spectral response of the normal contact stress between the receiving and the waveguide, due to an arbitrary input pulse excited by the transmitting transducer, is expressed in a form of explicit physical interpretations. The time histories of the response are then obtained through the inversion of the spectra by using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) method. Finally, some numerical results are presented to show the acousto-ultrasonic characteristics for transmitting and receiving contact-type transducers coupled to a composite beam.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

The problem considered is depicted in Fig. 1. A transmitting and a receiving transducers are coupled to a beam reinforced with unidirectional fibers, and spaced apart by a distance x_0 . The input pulse in the form of a normal contact stress is first injected on the surface of the beam through the transmitting transducer to excited ultrasonic waves. As the first wave front arrives at the receiver, the output will be sensed in a form of normal contact stress. Here the electron-mechanic and the mechanic-electron transfer segments are not further considered.

Fig. 1: Schematic of acousto-ultrasonic configuration

This does not affect the investigation in this paper, since the further consideration of these two segments only needs to introduce two transduction ratios [10].

Using the Timoshenko beam theory, the equations governing the motion of the beam considered can be shown as follows

$$G_{LT} Ak \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = q(x, t) \quad (1)$$

$$G_{LT} Ak \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \varphi \right) + E_L I \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} = \rho I \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2} \quad (2)$$

where t is the time variable, x the space variable referring to the coordinate system with the x -axis parallel to the fibers as shown in Fig. 1, E_L, G_{LT} are the Young's moduli and the shear moduli, respectively, and the subscripts L and T denote the directions parallel and normal to the fibers, respectively, ρ, A, I are the mass density, cross sectional area and the cross sectional area inertia moment of the beam, respectively, and k is the shear coefficient with a fixed value of 0.833 for the case of rectangular cross-section under consideration. Here $w(x, t)$ denotes the transverse displacement of the beam, $\varphi(x, t)$ the slope of the cross section, and $q(x, t)$ the distributed force exerted on the surface of the beam by the transmitting and the receiving transducers.

To simplify the analysis of the problem it is assumed that: (1) the pressure distribution of the transducers is in a parabolic form⁷; (2) the contact area between the contact-type receiver and the beam is so small that the displacement of the receiver can be taken as that of the beam at the center of the contact area.

From the first assumption the term $q(x, t)$ in Eq. (1) can be expressed as

$$q(x, t) = [H(x + a_1) - H(x - a_1)] \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a_1^2} \right) f(t) + [H(x - x_0 + a_2) - H(x - x_0 - a_2)] \left(1 - \frac{(x - x_0)^2}{a_2^2} \right) \sigma(t) \quad (3)$$

in which a_1 and a_2 are apertures of the transmitting and receiving transducers, respectively, $H(x)$ stands for the Heaviside function, $f(t)$ is the normal stress exerted on the beam by the transmitting transducer, and $\sigma(t)$ the normal stress sensed by the receiving transducer, which is the unknown function to be determined

Considering the motion of the receiving transducer and noting the second assumption above gives

$$M \frac{d^2 w(x, t)}{dt^2} = -a_2 \sigma(t) \quad (4)$$

in which M denotes the mass of the receiving transducer.

Applying Fourier time transform and spatial transform defined as

$$\bar{g}(x, \omega) = \int_0^{\infty} g(x, t) e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{g}(\kappa, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} g(x, t) e^{-i\kappa x} dx \quad (6)$$

to Eqs. (1-2) on t and x , respectively, and solving the resulting equations, the transformed solutions for $\tilde{w}(\kappa, \omega)$ and $\tilde{\varphi}(\kappa, \omega)$ are obtained as follows

$$\tilde{w}(\kappa, \omega) = (E_L I \kappa^2 + G_{LT} Ak - \rho I \omega^2) \tilde{q} / \Delta \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{\varphi}(\kappa, \omega) = -i\kappa G_{LT} Ak \tilde{q} / \Delta \quad (8)$$

with

$$\Delta = \rho G_{LT} A^2 k \left[\frac{E_L I}{\rho A} \kappa^4 - \frac{I}{A} \left(1 + \frac{E_L}{G_{LT} k} \right) \kappa^2 \omega^2 - \omega^2 + \frac{\rho I}{G_{LT} A k} \omega^4 \right] \quad (9)$$

The spatial Fourier inverse transform corresponding to Eq. (6)

$$g(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \tilde{g}(\kappa, t) e^{i\kappa x} d\kappa \quad (10)$$

is applied to Eq. (7) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x, \omega) = & \frac{\bar{f}(\omega)}{2\pi} \int_{-a_1}^{a_1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(1 - \frac{s^2}{a_1^2} \right) (E_L I \kappa^2 + G_{LT} A k - \rho I \omega^2) e^{i\kappa(x-s)} / \Delta ds d\kappa \\ & + \frac{\bar{\sigma}(\omega)}{2\pi} \int_{-a_2}^{a_2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(1 - \frac{\tau^2}{a_2^2} \right) (E_L I \kappa^2 + G_{LT} A k - \rho I \omega^2) e^{-i\kappa(\tau+x_0-x)} / \Delta d\tau d\kappa \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Additionally, applying the Fourier time transform Eq. (5) to the Eq. (4), we obtain

$$\bar{w}(x_0, \omega) = \frac{a_2 \bar{\sigma}(\omega)}{M \omega^2} \quad (12)$$

Setting $x = x_0$ in Eq. (11) and then comparing the resulting equation with Eq. (12), the unknown $\bar{\sigma}(\omega)$ can be finally expressed as follows

$$\bar{\sigma}(\omega) = \frac{M \omega^2 I_2 \bar{f}(\omega)}{2\pi a_2 - M \omega^2 I_1} \quad (13)$$

in which

$$I_1 = 2 \int_0^{a_2} \left(1 - \frac{\tau^2}{a_2^2} \right) I_1^* d\tau \quad (14)$$

$$I_2 = \int_{-a_1}^{a_1} \left(1 - \frac{s^2}{a_1^2} \right) I_2^* ds \quad (15)$$

with

$$I_1^* = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (E_L I \kappa^2 + G_{LT} A k - \rho I \omega^2) e^{i\kappa \tau} / \Delta d\kappa \quad (16)$$

$$I_2^* = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (E_L I \kappa^2 + G_{LT} A k - \rho I \omega^2) e^{i\kappa(x_0-s)} / \Delta d\kappa \quad (17)$$

For evaluating the integrals I_1^* and I_2^* , we now examine the roots of $\Delta=0$, i. e.

$$\frac{E_L I}{\rho A} \kappa^4 - \frac{I}{A} \left(1 + \frac{E_L}{G_{LT} k} \right) \kappa^2 \omega^2 - \omega^2 + \frac{\rho I}{G_{LT} A k} \omega^4 = 0 \quad (18)$$

Solving this equation for κ gives four possible roots. The first two roots are always of the following form for any frequency

$$\kappa_1, \kappa_2 = \pm \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} + \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right) \omega^2 + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} - \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right)^2 \omega^4 + \frac{1}{c_0^2 \alpha^2} \omega^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

with

$$c_0 = \sqrt{\frac{E_L}{\rho}}, \quad c_s = \sqrt{\frac{G_{LT}k}{\rho}}, \quad \alpha = \sqrt{\frac{I}{A}} \quad (20a,c)$$

while the forms of the other two roots are dependent on the magnitude of ω relative to a fixed value $\omega_c = \sqrt{G_{LT}k / \rho I}$, which can be expressed as:

when $|\omega| > \omega_c$,

$$\kappa_3, \kappa_4 = \pm \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} + \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right) \omega^2 - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} - \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right)^2 \omega^4 + \frac{1}{c_0^2 \alpha^2} \omega^2} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (21)$$

when $|\omega| \leq \omega_c$,

$$\kappa_3, \kappa_4 = \pm i\gamma, \quad (22)$$

with

$$\gamma = \pm \left[\sqrt{\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} - \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right)^2 \omega^4 + \frac{1}{c_0^2 \alpha^2} \omega^2} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} + \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right) \omega^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (23)$$

From Eqs. (16,17) it is easily seen that these roots obtained are four simple poles of the integrands of I_1^* and I_2^* . With this knowledge, the evaluation of these two integrals can be carried out by the residue theory. Omitting the lengthy procedure, the final results are given as follows

$$I_1^* = -\frac{\pi}{EI} \left[\frac{\gamma e^{-\gamma\tau}}{(\gamma^2 + \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} + \frac{\kappa_1 \sin \kappa_1 \tau}{(\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} \right], \quad |\omega| \leq \omega_c \quad (24)$$

$$I_1^* = -\frac{\pi}{EI} \left[\frac{\kappa_1 \sin \kappa_1 \tau}{(\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} - \frac{\kappa_3 \sin \kappa_3 \tau}{(\kappa_3^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} \right], \quad |\omega| > \omega_c \quad (25)$$

$$I_2^* = -\frac{\pi}{EI} \left[\frac{\gamma e^{-\gamma(x_0-s)}}{(\gamma^2 + \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} + \frac{\kappa_1 \sin[\kappa_1(x_0-s)]}{(\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} \right], \quad |\omega| \leq \omega_c \quad (26)$$

$$I_2^* = -\frac{\pi}{EI} \left[\frac{\kappa_1 \sin[\kappa_1(x_0-s)]}{(\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} - \frac{\kappa_3 \sin[\kappa_3(x_0-s)]}{(\kappa_3^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} \right], \quad |\omega| > \omega_c \quad (27)$$

in which

$$\delta = \left[\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} - \frac{1}{c_s^2} \right)^2 \omega^2 + \frac{4}{c_0^2 q^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (28)$$

Substituting Eqs. (24-27) into Eqs. (14-15) and then integrating with respect to τ or s yields

$$I_1 = -\frac{2\pi}{EI a_2^2} \left[\frac{-2 + \gamma^2 a_2^2 + 2(\gamma a_2 + 1)e^{-\gamma a_2}}{\gamma^2 (\gamma^2 + \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} + \frac{\kappa_1^2 a_2^2 - 2\kappa_1 a_2 \sin \kappa_1 a_2 - 2(\cos \kappa_1 a_2 - 1)}{\kappa_1^2 (\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} \right], \quad |\omega| \leq \omega_c \quad (29)$$

$$I_1 = -\frac{2\pi}{EI a_2^2} \left[\frac{\kappa_1^2 a_2^2 - 2\kappa_1 a_2 \sin \kappa_1 a_2 - 2(\cos \kappa_1 a_2 - 1)}{\kappa_1^2 (\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} - \frac{\kappa_3^2 a_2^2 - 2\kappa_3 a_2 \sin \kappa_3 a_2 - 2(\cos \kappa_3 a_2 - 1)}{\kappa_3^2 (\kappa_3^2 - \omega^2 / c_s^2) \delta \omega} \right], \quad |\omega| > \omega_c \quad (30)$$

$$I_2 = -\frac{2\pi}{Ela_2^2} \left\{ \frac{(\gamma a_1 + 1)e^{-\gamma(x_0 + a_1)} + (\gamma a_1 - 1)e^{-\gamma(x_0 - a_1)}}{\gamma^2(\gamma^2 + \omega^2/c_s^2)\delta\omega} + \frac{\{\cos[\kappa_1(x_0 - a_1)] - \cos[\kappa_1(x_0 + a_1)]\} - \kappa_1 a_1 \{\sin[\kappa_1(x_0 - a_1)] + \sin[\kappa_1(x_0 + a_1)]\}}{\kappa_1^2(\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2/c_s^2)\delta\omega} \right\},$$

$$|\omega| \leq \omega_c \quad (31)$$

$$I_2 = -\frac{2\pi}{Ela_2^2} \left\{ \frac{\{\cos[\kappa_1(x_0 - a_1)] - \cos[\kappa_1(x_0 + a_1)]\} - \kappa_1 a_1 \{\sin[\kappa_1(x_0 - a_1)] + \sin[\kappa_1(x_0 + a_1)]\}}{\kappa_1^2(\kappa_1^2 - \omega^2/c_s^2)\delta\omega} - \frac{\{\cos[\kappa_3(x_0 - a_1)] - \cos[\kappa_3(x_0 + a_1)]\} - \kappa_3 a_1 \{\sin[\kappa_3(x_0 - a_1)] + \sin[\kappa_3(x_0 + a_1)]\}}{\kappa_3^2(\kappa_3^2 - \omega^2/c_s^2)\delta\omega} \right\},$$

$$|\omega| > \omega_c \quad (32)$$

Having obtained the integrals I_1 and I_2 , from Eq. (13), the dynamic response of the contact stress between the receiving transducer and the beam waveguide in the frequency domain can be finally expressed as an explicit expression. From this expression it can be observed that: (1) the output of the system consists of two wave modes, with one being a traveling wave for any frequency, and the other when $|\omega| \leq |\omega_c|$ occurring in a form of an edge wave exponentially decaying in the x direction, and when $|\omega| > |\omega_c|$ a traveling wave; (2) each wave mode constitution has two wave fronts issued from two specific transmitting source points, respectively, one being the farthest with respect to the receiver and the other the nearest.

Using the fast Fourier Transform (FFT) technique, based on Eqs. (13, 29-32) the time domain response of the receiving transducer can be further obtained.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, some numerical results are presented graphically to show the ultrasonic input-output characteristics for transmitting and receiving longitudinal transducers coupled to a composite beam.

For the numerical results given in this paper, the parameters for the composite beam and the mass of the transducers are chosen as: $h = 2 \text{ mm}$, $b = 20 \text{ mm}$, $E_L = 38.6 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{LT} = 4.14 \text{ GPa}$, $\rho = 1.8 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $M = 0.01 \text{ kg}$, and the input is assumed to be the delayed sine pulse of time duration $f(t) = \sin(2\pi t/T)$ for $0 < t < T$; 0 for $t \geq 0$, where T is called as the input pulse width.

Fig. 2 shows a typical time history of the output of the receiving transducer, in which $T = 4 \mu\text{s}$. It can be observed that in this figure there exist three special instants: one is the beginning instant of the output response, which is denoted by S , and the other two are the instants at which the output response experience two peaks, which are denoted by M_1 and M_2 , respectively.

In order to analyze the physical interpretation of the above characteristic points, the group wave velocity c_{g1} and c_{g2} for the two wave modes involved in the output can be obtained by substituting Eqs. (19-21) into the relations

$$c_{g1} = d\omega / d\kappa_1, \quad c_{g2} = d\omega / d\kappa_3 \quad (33a,b)$$

Then the two maximum group velocities, denoted by $c_{g1\max}$ and $c_{g2\max}$ of the two wave modes, can be evaluated. Using these two maximums, the two earliest instants for the two wave mode excited by the transmitting transducer to arrive at the receiving transducer, are defined by the following equations

$$t_{s1} = (x_0 - a_1 - a_2) / c_{g1\max}, \quad t_{s2} = (x_0 - a_1 - a_2) / c_{g2\max} \quad (34a,b)$$

Fig. 2: Time history of the output $\sigma(t)$ for $x_0=150\text{mm}$, $a_1=a_2=10\text{mm}$, $T=4\mu\text{s}$

Fig. 3: Time history of the output $\sigma(t)$ for $x_0=100\text{mm}$, $a_1=a_2=10\text{mm}$, $T=4\mu\text{s}$

Fig. 4: Time history of the output $\sigma(t)$ for $x_0=150\text{mm}$, $a_1=a_2=10\text{mm}$, $T=3\mu\text{s}$

Fig. 5: Time history of the output $\sigma(t)$ for $x_0=150\text{mm}$, $a_1=a_2=5\text{mm}$, $T=3\mu\text{s}$

Through the above derivation and evaluation it is found that the instant obtained from Eq. (34b) is coincident with that marked by S in Fig. 2. This implies that the beginning point of the output response corresponds to the earliest arrival instant of the second mode components. It is evident that this conclusion is correct.

For examining the two peak instants, the instants when the components with maximum amplitude in frequency domain, respectively, issued from the two edges of the transmitting transducer, arrive at the center of the receiving transducer, are evaluated by

$$t_{M1} = (x_0 - a_1) / c^*, \quad t_{M2} = (x_0 + a_1) / c^* \quad (35a,b)$$

where c^* is the velocity of the component. It is found that the instants obtained from Eq. (35a,b) are in perfect agreement with those pinpointed by M_1 and M_2 in Fig. 2. This implies that the two maximum points of the output correspond to the two instants of the components of maximum amplitude issued from the two edges of the transmitting transducer arriving at the center of the receiving transducer.

To clarify the effects of the space between the transmitting and receiving transducers, the input pulse width and the aperture of the transducers on the output of the system, some numerical results for various values of such parameters are presented Figs. 3-5. Comparing Fig. 3 with Fig. 2, it can be observed that with an increase of the space between the transmitting and receiving transducers, the maximum output amplitude decreases. From Figs. 4 and 2, it can be seen that narrowing the input pulse width will lead to increase of high frequency components, but the maximum of the total output will decline. It is seen from the comparison of Fig. 5 with Fig. 2 that the smaller the aperture of the transducers is, the larger the amplitude of the output and the smaller the interval between its two maximum points. Obviously, these characteristics are all reasonable.

It should be noted that the numerical results given above are just the stress sensed by receiving transducers. For simulating the voltage output signals, it is required to incorporate the electron-mechanic transduction ratios of the transducers in the above analysis.

From the above numerical calculations and the features of the analytical method presented in the preceding sections it can be seen that although in this paper we only investigated the acousto-ultrasonic characteristics of a simple beam reinforced with unidirectional fibers paper, compared to the present wave path tracing method this investigation has provided a feasible approach for quantitatively analyzing the acousto-ultrasonic characteristics of complex structures. From this approach it may be possible to construct more reasonable and accurate stress wave factor definitions in which the influences of external testing conditions, such as the geometric characteristics of tested structures, transducers' spectral characteristics, mass or mounting pressure, aperture, spacing distance, coupling agent and so-on, can be eliminated or reduced as substantially as possible. This is of significance for improvement the current acousto-ultrasonic technique.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, the acousto-ultrasonic input-output characteristics for transmitting and receiving contact-type transducers coupled to a composite beam have been investigated. An analytical method is developed. Some characteristic points arising in the output response are analyzed. The effects of the space between the transmitting and the receiving transducers, the input pulse width and the aperture of the transducers on the output of the AU system are examined. The results obtained in this paper can be used to make optimum design of the AU system, and the analysis method can be easily extend to some more complicated cases such as multiple transducers case.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research has been supported by grants from Australian Research Council and from China Jiangsu Provincial Natural Science Foundation.

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